

Understanding Mob Violence: Some Theoretical Insights

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Introduction :

The theoretical underpinnings of mob violence are derived from the broader area of collective violence and collective behaviour. Before we attempt to examine mob violence, we need to define and differentiate a number of related terms and concepts. The term ‘collective’ may refer to something ‘done by people acting as a group’ or something ‘shared by every member of a group of people’. The term ‘collective behaviour’ refers to a diverse set of behaviours in which large number of people participates. Specifically, collective behaviour is used for ‘relatively spontaneous’ and ‘relatively unstructured’ behaviour performed by large number of individuals. These individuals are either acting with or being influenced by other individuals in the group. ‘*Relatively spontaneous*’ means that the behaviour has some spontaneity, but are also planned to some extent. ‘*Relatively unstructured*’ means that there may be some organisation and predictability to the behaviour, but may also be unorganised and unpredictable to some extent. Some forms of collective behaviour are more spontaneous and unstructured than others. Similarly, some forms of collective behaviour involve individuals acting together while others involve individuals being influenced by each other. In contrast to ‘conventional behaviour’ such as what happens in workplace, classroom or other settings of everyday behaviour, collective behaviour is considered to be less spontaneous and less structured.

As noted earlier, a number of miscellaneous behaviours are called collective behaviour that are classified on the basis of some key features and often have nothing in common with each other. Common forms of collective behaviour include crowds, mobs, panics, riots, disaster behaviour, rumours, mass hysteria, moral panics, and fads and crazes. Some forms of collective behaviour involve people who are generally present at the same place and interacting with each other such as crowds, panics, riots and disasters. There are other forms which involve people who are perhaps located hundreds or thousands of kilometres away from each other but share same concerns or beliefs, such as rumours, mass hysteria, moral panics, fads and crazes. Social movements are another common form of collective behaviour, which has gained a lot of scholarly attention since the 1960s and 1970s, making it one of the most extensively studied forms of collective behaviour.

Collective behaviour results from some common stimulus or influence that garners a response from a 'collectivity'. A relatively large number of people who mutually engage in bypassing or subverting established institutional patterns and structures can be defined as 'collectivity'. Such voluntary and often spontaneous activities involving a large number of people that goes against dominant-group norms and values are referred to as collective behaviour. Unlike the organisational behaviour characterising corporations and voluntary associations, collective behaviour is devoid of a set division of labour, hierarchy of authority and established rules and procedures. In contrast to the institutional behaviour found in education, religion or politics, collective behaviour is not governed by any institutional norms.

Defining Collective Behaviour :

Collective behaviour is when a sizable but loosely organised group of people engage in various types of activities. Such episodes are often spontaneous; stemming from a shared experience among the members of the group prompting a sense of common identity and interest. The unpredictable nature of collective behaviour results from the group's informal structure. It may include loosely organised activities like crowds, panics, fads, fashions, crazes, etc. and other more organised phenomena such as reforms and social movements. The study of collective behaviour is different from the study of individual behaviour as it focuses on groups

and not individuals. But these studies often focus on the attitudes and motivations of individuals in these group settings. Collective behaviour may look like organised group behaviour as it also comprises of people acting together as a group. However, organised group behaviour follows well-established rules, norms and traditions with clear purpose, membership, leadership and method of operation. Collective behaviour, on the other hand, is more spontaneous and consequently more volatile and less predictable in nature.

The term ‘collective behaviour’ was coined by U.S. Sociologist Robert E. Park, who defined it as “the behaviour of individuals under the influence of an impulse that is common and collective, an impulse, in other words, that is the result of social interaction.” He emphasised on the distinctive group process that results in people engaging in collective behaviour. He pointed out that people participating in various forms of collective behaviour, such as crowds or fads, share an attitude or behave in similar fashion. It is not because of any established rule or authority, but because of a distinctive group process. Collective behaviour is often quite volatile due to the lack of formal rules that govern group behaviour. There are no ways to distinguish between members and outsiders or identify group leader, no rules to establish aims of the collectivity, no set norms for group behaviour and no established method for collective decision making. The leader of a mob can become the target of the mob in a matter of minutes.

Even though collective behaviour generally lacks any set rules and norms, some scholars have focussed on the question of how rules and patterns emerge within the collectivity that is related to the surrounding social structure. Ralph H. Turner and Lewis M. Killian defined collective behaviour on the basis of “the spontaneous development of norms and organization which contradict or reinterpret the norms and organization of society.” Similar to this, Neil J. Smelser defined collective behaviour as “mobilization on the basis of a belief which redefines social action.” This distinctive ‘belief’, defined as the general conception of events for the group members, provides the basis for the establishment of distinct and stable organization within the collectivity. Smelser’s definition of collective behaviour draws attention to the unique manner in which group members perceive reality, without which they will not engage in collective behaviour. Sociologist Herbert Blumer pointed out that collective behaviour consists of a desire for social

change and defined it as “a collective enterprise to establish a new order of life.” This definition has been criticised as it fails to explain certain forms of collective behaviour, such as lynchings and panics, which are not meant for the reconstruction of society.

Different forms of Collective Behaviour :

People engaging in collective behaviour may be divided into crowds and masses. A crowd refers to a large number of people who are in each other’s immediate vicinity, such as people watching movie at a theatre or people attending a sporting event (Lofland, 1993). In contrast, a mass is a large number of people who share an interest in a specific idea or issue but are not in one another’s immediate vicinity (Lofland, 1993). Herbert Blumer (1969) provided a typology of crowds on the basis of their purpose and dynamics, which are casual crowds, conventional crowds, expressive crowds, and acting crowds. Another type of crowds which has been distinguished by other scholars is protest crowds. Collective behaviour may also be distinguished by the dominant emotion expressed by the group. John Lofland defines dominant expression as the “publicly expressed feeling perceived by participants and observers as the most prominent in an episode of collective behaviour” (1993, p.72). Lofland has pointed out that the three most fundamental emotions found in collective behaviour are fear, hostility and joy; however, other predominant emotions found in some forms of collective behaviour are grief, disgust, surprise or shame.

A casual crowd can be described as a collection of people who happen to be present at the place at the same time, with no real common bond or identity and no long-term purpose. For instance, spontaneous gathering of people waiting to cross the street at a busy intersection in a city is a causal crowd. It can be argued that this group of people do have a common goal to some degree as they are all waiting to cross the street, but this is a temporary goal and the gathering of people disappears rather quickly once this goal is achieved. As Erich Goode points out, “members of casual crowds have little else in common except their physical location” (1992, p. 22). Goode (1992) has argued that the behaviour followed by casual crowds is relatively structured and follows the conventional norms expected of such settings; hence, they are not really a form of collective behaviour. Conventional

crowds can be defined as group of people who share a common purpose and who have specifically gathered for a scheduled event, such as classroom lectures, concerts, ceremonies and religious festivals, etc. All such events have established schedules and norms and interaction among people at these events is very much likely as these events occur regularly. In fact, the crowd is essential to the events as these would not occur without the crowd. Goode (1992) again argues that these crowds should not be considered a form of collective behaviour as their behaviour is relatively structured and follows conventional behaviour. An expressive crowd can be defined as a collection of people who have gathered to be excited and to express emotions, such as political rally for a candidate or celebratory event for a sports team. Goode (1992) argues that for expressive crowds, being part of the crowd is the main purpose and the crowd activity is the end in itself. Take the case of conventional crowds, people gathered to watch a movie or hear a lecture, being part of the crowd is not relevant for them. On the contrary, in expressive crowds, people want to belong to the crowd, become a member and take part in crowd behaviour like screaming, shouting, cheering or clapping to express their emotions. A conventional crowd can turn into an expressive crowd if people decide to express an emotion like audience at a movie start shouting for some reason. As indicated with this example, it is not always clear to differentiate between a conventional crowd and an expressive crowd. However, as expressive crowds are primarily engaged in being excited and expressing emotions, these crowds are definitely a form of collective behaviour.

The fourth types of crowd, an acting crowd goes one step beyond an expressive crowd and also engage in some kind of violent or destructive behaviour. A primary example of an acting crowd is a 'mob', which can be defined as an intensely emotional crowd that either commits or is ready to commit violence. According to a dictionary of psychology, "a *crowd* is a collection of people who share a common interest and whose emotions may be easily aroused; a *mob* is a crowd acting under strong emotional conditions that often lead to violence or illegal acts" (Chaplin 1985). Mob violence dissipates fairly quickly as soon as the target has been injured, killed or destroyed. Riots tend to last longer than mob violence. Riots can be defined as violent crowd behaviour without any specific target and often driven by deep-rooted emotions. Riots can result from various circumstances. Riots are often triggered by hostility, fear or anger; but rioting can also occur when people

are gathered to express joy and exuberance. For instance, a crowd gathered to celebrate victory of a sports team can suddenly start destroying property and committing other violent acts. Levin & Mehlinger (1975) describes riots as “an unplanned or unorganized expression of anger or rage, without a focused goal”. But participants of a riot often do have shared motives. Another form of acting crowd is ‘panic’, which is described as a sudden reaction by a crowd that turns self-destructive, like people stomping each other while trying to flee from a theatre when fire breaks out. In some cases, acting crowds become really large and get so out of control that they develop into full-scale riots. Lastly, the type of crowds engaged in activities that intend to achieve specific political goals, are referred to as protest crowds. Examples of protest crowds include sit-ins, strikes, boycotts, marches or blockades. Sometimes, protests are acts of civil disobedience which may become violent, such as during a confrontation between protesters and police officers, turning protest crowds into acting crowds. Another form of collective behaviour is ‘social movement’ which can be defined as an organised effort by a large number of people to either bring about or hamper social change. Scholars also study the collective behaviour people engage in during and after disasters, which is termed as ‘disaster behaviour’. Contrary to common belief that people only care about themselves during a disaster, research suggests that people behave the opposite under such circumstances. People generally stay calm and try to help others during a disaster.

All the different types of collective behaviour discussed so far, i.e. crowds, riots and disaster behaviour, involve people present in close proximity and physically interacting with each other. However, there are some forms of collective behaviour that involve people located far away from each other geographically and not physically interacting. These people, however, have certain common beliefs and perceptions shared among them that can be classified as collective behaviour. These beliefs and perceptions are classified into two broad categories: a) rumours, mass hysteria and moral panics; and b) fads and crazes. The first category, including rumours, mass hysteria and moral panics, all stem from strongly held beliefs and perceptions that are either gross distortions of reality or not true at all. A rumour is an unsubstantiated story based on unreliable sources that are passed on from one person to another person. A rumour can sometimes turn out to be true, but mostly these are either false or distortion or exaggeration of the facts. Goode (1992)

argues that its defining feature is that it is not based on any reliable evidence. Rumours can spread very quickly over the internet and via social media in the current electronic age. Similarly, mass hysteria is when people at large have an intense fear or concern for a perceived danger. This widespread fear and concern often turn out to be false or greatly exaggerated. Mass hysterias are relatively rare. A moral panic is quite similar to mass hysteria and refers to a large number of people sharing a strong concern over a perceived threat to the moral order. These also turn out to be greatly exaggerated or completely false. There are certain behaviours that are considered moral problems and invoke an extreme concern from people at large such as drug use or sexual activity. However, these concerns are not based on reality and the dangers posed by these problems are blown out of proportions. Nonetheless, people seek to alleviate their concerns with various actions to fight the moral problem.

Theories of Crowd Behaviour :

This section of the paper deals with the major theories of crowd behaviour. One of the earliest theorists to provide a perspective on collective behaviour was Gustave Le Bon, a French scholar who studied crowd psychology. Le Bon (1895) focussed on the socio-psychological aspects of collective behaviour in his contagion theory. He attempted to explain the ways in which moods, attitudes and behaviour are communicated and accepted by members of the group (Turner and Killian, 1993). Le Bon (1895) argues that people believe they become invisible and invulnerable in a crowd and hence are more likely to engage in violent antisocial behaviour. Le Bon also suggested that a crowd takes on a life of its own that is larger than the beliefs or actions of any one person. As people feel anonymous in a crowd, they stop acting rationally and transform into a single organism with a collective mind. He asserts that emotions like fear or hate become contagious in a crowd as people's sense of personal responsibility disappears in a crowd. People are ready to do things in a crowd that they will never do when acting alone. Robert E. Park believed that Le Bon's analysis of collective behaviour lacked several important elements. While investigating crowd behaviour, he was fascinated by the fact that people could throw away their established routines and the strong hold of culture to develop a new social order in a collectivity. Park modified Le Bon's Contagion theory and added the concepts of social unrest and circular reaction. Park explained that social

unrest is transmitted through a process of circular reaction. The discontent felt by one person in a group is communicated to the other person and that person, in turn, reflects the discontent back to the first person (Park and Burgess, 1921).

Another significant theory of crowd behaviour is the Convergence theory which focuses on the shared emotions, goals and beliefs that people bring to the crowd. Turner and Killian (1993) argue that people have a general inclination to participate in certain types of activities due to their individual characteristics. This perspective explains that people try to find like-minded people to form a collectivity where they can express their personal predispositions. Convergence theory argues that people's behaviour in a crowd is not irrational, even if people may present their true selves in crowds. In fact, for people with common emotions and beliefs, this behaviour is highly predictable. Scholars have applied Convergence theory to a wide range of collective behaviour, from lynch mobs to environmental movements. Hadley Cantril (1941), while studying lynchings in the United States, found that the participants of these incidences shared some common attributes. Generally, the participants were poor working-class whites who felt that their social status was threatened by the success of African Americans. These characteristics made them more inclined to joining a lynch mob, even if they were unfamiliar with the target of the lynching. Convergence theory brings attention to the certain attributes of individuals that initially brings them together to engage in certain collective behaviour. It can be anything from racial hatred to fear of environmental problems that poses a direct threat to them. However, this perspective fails to explain the differences between the attitudes and characteristics of individuals who engage in collective behaviour from those who do not act in similar way.

The third major theory of crowd behaviour is the Emergent Norm theory which focuses on how social norms play an important role in shaping crowd behaviour. Proposed by Turner and Killian (1972), it draws on the interactionist perspective and asserts that crowds develop their own understanding of a situation and establish behavioural norms to fit the occasion. According to them, emergent norm occurs when people think of a new situation as highly unusual or interpret a long-standing situation in a different manner (1993, p.13). Scholars use emergent norm to understand how individuals in a collectivity make sense of the situation, how they interpret the activities they engage in and what types of norms are

involved in that situation. Emergent norms, in certain situations, provide people the shared conviction to disregard ordinary rules like waiting in lines or taking turns or behaving courteously toward a speaker. For instance, participants may define the acts of mass looting as punishing those who are exploitative and taking what rightfully belongs to them. As soon as the crowd agrees on the norms, the collectivity is expected to adhere to them. If the crowd members develop a norm that justifies looting and destroying property, they will celebrate those who abide by the norm and ridicule those who are not willing to adhere to the norm. Emergent norm theory suggests that crowds are not irrational, but develop new norms rationally to fit the need of the immediate situation. However, this theory fails to specify what is considered to be a norm, how a new norm emerges and how they are communicated so quickly and get accepted by a large number of participants. It has been argued that in a crowd, there is no single dominant norm that gets universally accepted. Instead, a number of norms emerge that are specific to various types of participants than the whole collectivity (Snow, Zurcher and Peters, 1981).

Neal Smelser (1963) developed the Value-added theory which specifically focussed on social movements. Smelser worked under the assumption that the development of social movements requires certain necessary conditions. He named his theory after the economic concept of value-addition where each step of the production process adds something of value to the product. Smelser (1963) derived six necessary conditions that combine or interact in certain situation to produce social movements. First condition is termed structural conduciveness which implies that people need to be aware of a significant problem and they should have the opportunity to engage in collective action. Social movements will occur when a specific source of the problem can be singled out, when people do not have proper channels for expressing grievances and when the aggrieved have opportunities to communicate with one another. Second condition is termed structural strain which emphasises the strain put on the system when the society or community is unable to meet people's expectations to address a problem. People believe that the problem exists because authorities have not taken the required action which leads to tension and conflict in society. The third condition is spread of a generalized belief when a definite statement of the problem develops and a shared view of the causes, effects and possible solutions emerges. The fourth condition is termed as precipitating factors meaning an inciting incident or a dramatic event that reinforces the existing

generalised belief. Some movements emerge from a long-standing threat while others emerge from a sudden problem. The fifth condition is called mobilization for action when leaders start to merge to give direction to people and organise them for a movement. The sixth and final condition is social control factors that takes into account the degree of social control exerted by law and governance officials which can make it harder for a social movement to develop. Value-added theory enables researchers to understand the complex nature of social movements and test for the necessary and sufficient conditions that produce social movements.

Conclusion :

The term 'collective behaviour' was first used by Robert E. Park and elaborated on by Herbert Blumer, to refer to social processes that emerge in a spontaneous way and do not abide by the existing social structure. This paper was an attempt to understand the phenomenon of mob violence, which is a specific form of collective violence stemming from a specific type of collective behaviour. The main objective was to present the major theoretical and conceptual frameworks from the existing literature on collective behaviour and collective violence. It is in no way an exhaustive literature survey; rather the focus is on drawing out the foundational and relevant concepts for theorising the topic at hand. The major theories of collective behaviour, i.e. contagion theory, social unrest and circular norm, emergent norm theory, value-added theory, can be employed to understand various forms of collective behaviour.

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